

Prevalence and clustering of NANDA-I nursing diagnoses in the pre-hospital emergency care setting: A retrospective records review study

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Abstract

Aim: To determine the prevalence and clustering of NANDA-International nursing diagnoses in patients assisted by pre-hospital emergency teams.

Design: Retrospective descriptive study of electronic record review.

Methods: Episodes recorded during 2019, including at least a nursing diagnosis, were recovered from the electronic health records of a Spanish public emergency agency ($N=28,847$). Descriptive statistics were used to characterize the sample and determine prevalence. A two-step cluster analysis was used to group nursing diagnoses. A comparison between clusters in sociodemographic and medical problems was performed. Data were accessed in November 2020.

Results: Risk for falls (00155) (27.3%), Anxiety (00146) (23.2%), Acute pain (00132), Fear (00148) and Ineffective breathing pattern (00032) represented 96.1% of all recorded diagnoses. A six-cluster solution ($n=26,788$) was found. Five clusters had a single high-prevalence diagnosis predominance: Risk for falls (00155) in cluster 1, Anxiety (00146) in cluster 2, Fear (00148) in cluster 3, Acute pain (00132) in cluster 4 and Ineffective breathing pattern (00032) in cluster 6. Cluster 5 had several high prevalence diagnoses which co-occurred: Risk for unstable blood glucose level (00179), Ineffective coping (00069), Ineffective health management (00078), Impaired comfort (00214) and Impaired verbal communication (00051).

Conclusion: Five nursing diagnoses accounted for almost the entire prevalence. The identified clusters showed that pre-hospital patients present six patterns of nursing diagnoses. Five clusters were predominated by a predominant nursing diagnosis related to patient safety, coping, comfort, and activity/rest, respectively. The sixth cluster grouped several nursing diagnoses applicable to exacerbations of chronic diseases.

The authors have checked to make sure that our submission conforms as applicable to the Journal's statistical guidelines described here. There is a statistician on the author team (José Manuel Romero-Sánchez).

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Implications for the profession and/or patient care: Knowing the prevalence and clustering of nursing diagnoses allows a better understanding of the human responses of patients attended by pre-hospital emergency teams and increases the evidence of individualized/standardized care plans in the pre-hospital clinical setting.

Impact: What problem did the study address?

- There are different models of pre-hospital emergency care services.
- The use of standardized nursing languages in the pre-hospital setting is not homogeneous.
- Studies on NANDA-I nursing diagnoses in the pre-hospital context are scarce, and those available are conducted on small samples.

What were the main findings?

- This paper reports the study with the largest sample among the few published on NANDA-I nursing diagnoses in the pre-hospital care setting.
- Five nursing diagnoses represented 96.1% of all recorded. These diagnoses were related to patients' safety/protection and coping/stress tolerance.
- Patients attended by pre-hospital care teams are grouped into six clusters based on the nursing diagnoses, and this classification is independent of the medical conditions the patient suffers.

Where and on whom will the research have an impact?

Knowing the prevalence of nursing diagnoses allows a better understanding of the human responses of patients treated in the pre-hospital setting, increasing the evidence of individualized and standardized care plans for pre-hospital care.

Reporting method: STROBE checklist has been used as a reporting method.

No Patient or Public Contribution: Only patients' records were reviewed without further involvement.

KEYWORDS

cluster analysis, electronic health records, nursing diagnosis, nursing records, pre-hospital emergency care

1 | INTRODUCTION

Pre-hospital care is defined as the care and treatment given to people in danger of death due to an accident or sudden acute illness that needs to be transferred by ambulance or helicopter to health care facilities, such as the hospital emergency department (Ahl & Nyström, 2012; Péculo-Carrasco et al., 2022; Tibães et al., 2018). Pre-hospital emergency medical services (EMS) have evolved considerably since their beginnings (Coca et al., 2020). The activity and visibility of EMS have experienced an exponential increase during the last decades, trying to respond adequately to the emergencies that occur daily and due to natural or intentional catastrophes (Fàbrega & Canela, 2020). However, different EMS models currently coexist. Unlike pre-hospital emergency care models in which paramedics make up the emergency care teams, European models, including the Spanish model, integrate physicians and nurses into such resources. (Fàbrega & Canela, 2020; Palma et al., 2005). The pre-hospital emergency care nurses' clinical practice has traditionally consisted mainly

What does this paper contribute to the wider global clinical community?

- Knowing the prevalence and clustering of nursing diagnoses allows a better understanding of the human responses of patients treated in the pre-hospital setting.
- The top five most recorded nursing diagnoses in the pre-hospital care setting were related to patients' safety/protection and coping/stress tolerance.
- Patients attended by pre-hospital care teams are grouped into six clusters based on their nursing diagnoses, and this classification is independent of the medical conditions the patient suffers.

of monitoring the patient's health and performing technical interventions. Mota et al. (2019) state that pre-hospital nursing tends to

focus its care activity on the health/illness dichotomy and interdisciplinary actions (Mota et al., 2019, 2021). This role limitation is not only incompatible with the idea of professional autonomy in nursing (Briggs, 1991; Sánchez-Almagro et al., 2022). It also relegates holistic care of the critically ill patient to the sidelines (Torres et al., 2002), thus limiting the quality of the information contained in care records to the technical interventions developed and reducing the possibilities for research on the human responses presented by patients in the pre-hospital environment.

The international scientific literature on pre-hospital emergency care highlights interventions developed by professionals other than nurses. On the one hand, nurses do not provide this type of care in certain countries (Mota et al., 2021). On the other hand, due to an orientation of care focused on addressing the physical needs of patients due, among other elements, to the life-threatening nature of pathologies attended in pre-hospital emergency care (Sánchez-Almagro et al., 2022). This circumstance and the lack of global homogeneity of pre-hospital healthcare models (Fàbrega & Canela, 2020) could be conditioning the scarcity of studies with similar aims to compare the present study results.

Nurses must base their clinical practice on structured and evidence-based knowledge to consolidate the profession as a science. The nursing process is recognized as the foundation of nursing practice. It represents a nursing care and problem-solving structure and describes nursing as a profession based on establishing professional-patient relationships (Müller-Staub et al., 2015). Various international and national scientific associations dedicated to both the use of nursing standardized nursing languages and emergency care, such as The NANDA-International (NANDA-I) and the Spanish Association of Nomenclature, Taxonomy and Nursing Diagnosis (AENTDE) and the Spanish Society of Emergency Nursing (SEEUE), recommend the use of nursing process and nursing diagnosis to maintain scientific, professional, and quality assurance in order for a nursing language with a high degree of consensus and standardization to be achieved (Cachón-Pérez et al., 2021). As part of the nursing process, the nursing diagnosis represents the 'clinical judgement concerning a human response to health conditions/life processes, or a vulnerability for that response, by an individual, family, group, or community and provides the basis for selection of nursing interventions to achieve outcomes for which the nurse has accountability' (Herdman et al., 2021). The use of nursing diagnoses proposed by NANDA-I is recommended to identify the human responses that nurses address (Herdman et al., 2021). However, the use of the nursing process and the NANDA-I Nursing Diagnosis Classification (Herdman et al., 2021) are not yet systematized at the level of most pre-hospital EMS in the world. Their development in Spain is also irregular.

2 | BACKGROUND

The nursing process has been applied to pre-hospital emergency clinical practice for over a decade in Andalusia, a region in southern Spain (Bocanegra-Pérez et al., 2017). Moreover, NANDA-I nursing

diagnoses have been used to record human responses diagnosed by the nurse in electronic health records (EHR) (Coca et al., 2020). Nurses who work for the Andalusian EMS develop nursing care plans following the guidelines of the public EMS of the region (Medical Emergency Center 061. Andalusia, Spain). This orientation enables a holistic assessment and a universal approach to the human responses of patients assisted by these pre-hospital emergency nurses.

There is a paucity of solid knowledge on the prevalence and distribution of nursing diagnoses in pre-hospital care patients, with only a few studies reporting the nursing diagnoses found in these patients, and no none of them have been based on large databases (Cámara & Valenzuela, 2007; Coca et al., 2020; Cyrillo et al., 2009). Nonetheless, prevalence studies using large databases are essential to improving the knowledge of the epidemiology of NDs. Considering the NDs in a specific category of patients or a particular care unit can provide a picture of the most frequent nursing needs and, consequently, the outcome to achieve and the interventions to perform (D'Agostino et al., 2017).

Once the prevalence has been determined, it is possible to determine which human responses co-occur in these patients by grouping the nursing diagnoses that have been recorded. Nursing diagnosis patterns may allow healthcare teams to make a prognosis and identify the care trajectory compared with similar patients (D'Agostino et al., 2017). However, no study has been found that has previously addressed diagnostic patterns in pre-hospital patients empirically.

3 | THE STUDY

3.1 | Aim

This study aimed to determine the prevalence and clustering of NANDA-I nursing diagnoses in an extensive data set of episodes of patients assisted by pre-hospital emergency teams recorded in EHR.

4 | METHODS

4.1 | Design

A retrospective descriptive study was developed to determine the prevalence and clustering of NANDA-I nursing diagnoses in a public emergency care agency's electronic health record (EHR) in Andalusia, southern Spain.

4.2 | Sample/participants

Records of adult patients' episodes who were assisted and transferred to the hospital by pre-hospital emergency care teams during 2019 due to an emerging health problem were included. The patient episode refers to the entire period of care provided due to a particular condition or set of related conditions to an individual from the

initial point of contact with pre-hospital emergency services until the transfer of care to a hospital. Therefore, if the same patient has been attended to more than once during the period, each care instance was considered an independent episode. Records that met any of the following criteria were excluded: (a) records that did not include nursing diagnoses, (b) records of patients under 18 years of age and (c) records of patients with unknown age. Consequently, only cases with complete data on nursing diagnosis and other variables of interest were analysed. Given that the entire data set was available and feasible to analyse, it was decided to conduct a census instead of sampling.

4.3 | Data collection

The following variables were considered, followed by their possible observations or units of measurement:

- Sociodemographic variables: age (years) and sex (male, female, undetermined/unknown).
- Nursing diagnoses of the 2015–2017 edition of the NANDA-I Classification of Nursing Diagnoses (Herdman & Kamitsuru, 2014) (presence, absence). A series of predetermined diagnoses was pre-selected in the EHR to make it easier for nurses to record these diagnoses. This preselection was chosen on expert consensus based on the most frequent human responses in the pre-hospital emergency care setting identified by an agency committee. The nurses were also given a free text to include nursing diagnoses other than those pre-selected.
- Pre-hospital medical problems: *Trauma, Stroke, Acute neurology excluding stroke, Chest pain, Acute cardiology, Acute dyspnea, and Others* (presence, absence). The International Statistical Classification of Disease (ICD-9) medical diagnoses defined by the HEMS physician for each patient were aggregated within different pre-hospital medical problem categories.

The nursing staff recorded data in the EHR by typing with a digital pen on a portable touch-screen computer. The software has an intuitive interface that facilitates recording the care plan in selectable fields and drop-down menus in tabs that organize the data by each phase of the nursing process. Since a pre-hospital patient episode is usually relatively short, data are usually recorded only once per episode. Once the care plan is completed, a care report is automatically sent to the agency's data server and integrated into the patient's EHR.

The data needed for this study was retrieved from the EHR system and extracted by the agency's data manager and by a member of the research team using a query technique. The data was exported into tables, one table containing sociodemographic and medical diagnosis data and another NANDA-I nursing diagnoses expressed in a binary 'presence' or 'absence' format. Both were merged into a single table, and two research team members applied filters to retain only those cases that met the eligibility criteria. Once the table contained

only eligible cases, it was exported to IBM SPSS Statistics v.25 for Windows (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA).

4.4 | Ethical considerations

The Andalusian Biomedical Research Ethics Coordinating Committee approved the study in October 2020 (09/20). The research team received the data in an anonymized form. For this purpose, a code was assigned to each case that replaced the patients' personal identification numbers. Storing password-protected files on safe and secure computers was used to ensure protection from unauthorized access, corruption or digital data theft.

4.5 | Data analysis

Descriptive statistics were used to characterize the sample for sociodemographic variables and to determine the prevalence of recorded NANDA-I nursing diagnoses and pre-hospital medical problems. Continuous variables were summarized as mean, and standard deviation, and categorical variables were expressed as frequency and percentages. The normal distribution of the variables was verified using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov–Lilliefors test.

A cluster analysis was used to reveal profiles of the nursing diagnosis of patients who were attended to and transferred to the hospital by pre-hospital emergency care teams due to an emerging health problem. To establish distinct clusters showing trends in human responses that are frequent in the out-of-hospital setting, only those nursing diagnoses presented in more than 2% of the total episodes were considered. This cut-off point was chosen by representing the prevalence of diagnoses in a bar graph, ordered from most to least prevalent, and determining where an elbow occurred in the prevalence trend. This elbow occurred after the fourteenth diagnosis in descending order of prevalence. Diagnoses after this point were considered to have residual prevalence and did not enter the cluster analysis. In this case, they were those with a less than 2% prevalence. This heuristic decision was made to make the cluster solutions more interpretable. Therefore, only the following 14 nursing diagnoses were considered as clustering variables: Deficient knowledge (00126), Acute pain (00132), Anxiety (00146), Fear (00148), Risk for falls (00155), Ineffective breathing pattern (00032), Risk for unstable blood glucose level (00179), Impaired comfort (00214), Risk for injury (00035), Risk for infection (00004), Impaired verbal communication (00051), Ineffective coping (00069), Ineffective health management (00078) and Impaired physical mobility (00085).

The two-step cluster analysis method was chosen. Such a technique has several advantages compared to traditional techniques: using categorical, including binary variables, determining the number of clusters based on statistical measures of fit rather than on an arbitrary choice, allowing the exclusion of outliers that could affect the quality of clustering and is suitable for large datasets (Bacher et al., 2004; Chiu et al., 2001; IBM Corporation, 2021; Norušis, 2012;

Tkaczynski et al., 2010). The two-step cluster analysis involves two stages (Bacher et al., 2004; Chiu et al., 2001; Norušis, 2012). In the first step, the pre-clustering, original cases were grouped into pre-clusters based on log-likelihood distance. During the ple-clustering, a noise reduction was performed using outlier detection. The cases that did not fit into a substantive cluster were considered outlier and merged into a separate outlier cluster. All the nursing diagnoses included in the analysis were present in the outlier cluster with irregular prevalence and miscellaneous cooccurrence patterns that made them not fit in any of the other clusters. The cases of this outlier cluster were excluded from the second step (IBM Corporation, 2021). The second step selected the best number of clusters based on Schwartz's Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC). The best number of clusters was that the BIC became small, and the BIC change between the adjacent clusters was also small (Norušis, 2012).

After the optimal number of clusters was found, it was validated by assessing the quality and consistency of this cluster solution using three different approaches. First, the silhouette coefficient was determined. Silhouette Coefficient is a statistic that combines both cohesion (high similarity intra-cluster) and separation (high dissimilarity inter-clusters) to produce an overall measure of cluster validity. It ranges from -1 to 1 , and values above $.5$ were considered good quality. Therefore, the clustering was assumed to be successful (Wendler & Gröttrup, 2021). Second, chi-squared tests were performed to evaluate if the distribution of each nursing diagnosis included as clustering variables differed between clusters and the signification of this difference. Significant differences among clusters were expected. Third, cluster stability was tested. A suitable clustering method should yield similar partitions when applied to multiple datasets from the same distribution (Ullmann et al., 2022). Therefore, the same cluster procedures were applied to random subsamples of half of the cases of the total sample to verify if the cluster solution follows a consistent pattern.

Comparisons between clusters were made using Kruskal-Wallis and chi-square tests for continuous (age) and categorical data (gender, pre-hospital medical problem) correspondingly. Mann-Whitney U -test and chi-square tests were used for post-hoc pairwise comparisons.

Statistical data analysis was performed with IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, version 25 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). The results were considered significant if p was $<.05$.

5 | RESULTS

5.1 | Description of the participants

Sixty-one thousand six hundred and eight episodes of patients were attended and transferred to the hospital by pre-hospital emergency care teams recorded in the agency's ERH during 2019, of which 30,419 had at least one nursing diagnosis recorded. Ninety-six records of patients with unknown age and 1476 corresponding to patients under 18 were eliminated, resulting in a final population of 28,847 cases.

The participants ranged from 18 to 105 years of age, with a mean age of 61.64 (SD=19.33). Approximately 52.80% were identified as male, 46.37% as female and .83% as undetermined or unknown.

5.2 | Prevalence of nursing diagnoses

Table 1 reports the prevalence of nursing diagnoses in the episode records. A total of 41,942 nursing diagnoses corresponding to 49 different labels were recorded. Only 14 nursing diagnoses appeared in more than 2% of records. The most frequent nursing diagnoses recorded in pre-hospital care episodes were *Risk for falls* (00155) with 27.30% ($n=7876$) followed by *Anxiety* (00146) with 23.20% ($n=6699$), *acute pain* (00132) with 20.50% ($n=5920$), *Fear* (00148) with 18.20% ($n=5239$) and *Ineffective breathing pattern* (00032) with 6.90% ($n=1991$). 90.62% of the episodes had a single one (69.36%) or two (21.25%) diagnoses recorded.

5.3 | Cluster descriptions and cluster solution validation

In the two-step cluster analysis of 28,847 cases, 2059 outliers (7.1%) were detected outliers were excluded from the second step of cluster analysis and the rest of the related analyses. Therefore, 26,788 records were finally used for the cluster analysis.

Two-step cluster analysis revealed six clusters. Table 2 shows the cluster solution determined, the size and proportion of each diagnosis considered clustering variables for each. Five of the six clusters were dominated by a single diagnosis with the residual occurrence of others. However, a sixth cluster agglutinated several diagnoses with similar prevalence without a clear predominance. Figure 1 graphically represents the prevalence of nursing diagnosis per cluster.

Cluster 1 consisted of 5618 episodes and was dominated by the nursing diagnosis *Risk for falls* (00155) (safety/protection domain) (82.93%) and was named "Responses to security threats". Clusters 2 and 3, consisting of 4719 and 4206 episodes, respectively, had as predominant diagnoses from the coping/stress tolerance domain, *Anxiety* (00146) in the case of cluster 2 (77.95%) and *Fear* (00148) (88.29%) in cluster 3. These clusters were named 'Anxiety coping response' and 'Fear coping response'. Cluster 4, named 'Acute pain response', consisted of 5135 episodes and had *Acute pain* (00132) (Comfort domain) as the predominant diagnosis (99.53%). Cluster 5, made up of 5421 episodes and called 'Responses to exacerbations of chronic diseases', was the only cluster in which several diagnoses with high prevalence co-occurred, which were the following: *Risk for unstable blood glucose level* (00179) (Nutrition domain), *Ineffective coping* (00069) (Coping/stress tolerance domain), *Ineffective health management* (00078) (Health promotion domain), *Impaired comfort* (00214) (Comfort domain) and *Impaired verbal communication* (00051) (Perception/cognition domain). Cluster 6, consisting of 1689 episodes, showed the *Ineffective breathing pattern* (00032) (Activity/rest domain) as the predominant diagnosis and was named "Dyspnea response".

TABLE 1 Prevalence of nursing diagnoses in the recorded episodes with their frequency and the percentage of episodes in which each diagnosis is present.

Ranking	Nursing diagnosis	Frequencies (n)	Presence in episodes (%)
1	00155. Risk for falls	7876	27.30
2	00146. Anxiety	6699	23.20
3	00132. Acute pain	5920	20.50
4	00148. Fear	5239	18.20
5	00032. Ineffective breathing pattern	1991	6.90
6	00085. Impaired physical mobility	1477	5.10
7	00214. Impaired comfort	1146	4.00
8	00004. Risk for infection	1000	3.50
9	00078. Ineffective health management	948	3.30
10	00051. Impaired verbal communication	894	3.10
11	00069. Ineffective coping	876	3.00
12	00179. Risk for unstable blood glucose level	802	2.80
13	00035. Risk for injury	807	2.80
14	00126. Deficient knowledge	671	2.30
15	00240. Risk for decreased cardiac output	538	1.90
16	00039. Risk for aspiration	556	1.90
17	00128. Acute confusion	533	1.80
18	00046. Impaired skin integrity	528	1.80
19	00031. Ineffective airway clearance	402	1.40
20	00007. Hyperthermia	326	1.10
21	00099. Ineffective health maintenance	298	1.00
22	00205. Risk for shock	239	.80
23	00061. Caregiver role strain	191	.70
24	00092. Activity intolerance	213	.70
25	00133. Chronic pain	171	.60
26	00120. Situational low self-esteem	156	.50
27	00124. Hopelessness	149	.50
28	00062. Risk for caregiver role strain	136	.50
29	00231. Risk for frail elderly syndrome	120	.40
30	00074. Compromised family coping	125	.40
31	00098. Impaired home maintenance	103	.40

TABLE 1 (Continued)

Ranking	Nursing diagnosis	Frequencies (n)	Presence in episodes (%)
32	00123. Unilateral neglect	86	.30
33	00047. Risk for impaired skin integrity	91	.30
34	00060. Interrupted family processes	75	.30
35	00136. Grieving	68	.20
36	00054. Risk for loneliness	55	.20
37	00005. Risk for imbalanced body temperature	55	.20
38	00072. Ineffective denial	55	.20
39	00080. Ineffective family health management	56	.20
40	00083. Decisional conflict	66	.20
41	00135. Complicated grieving	24	.10
42	00139. Risk for self-mutilation	43	.10
43	00141. Posttrauma syndrome	25	.10
44	00210. Impaired resilience	29	.10
45	00006. Hypothermia	36	.10
46	00079. Non-compliance	20	.10
47	00118. Disturbed body image	7	.00
48	00181. Contamination	13	.00
49	00255. Chronic pain syndrome	8	.00

Note: The sum of the percentage of diagnoses present in the episodes is over 100% since a diagnosis can appear in more than one episode.

The following results were found regarding the validation of the clusters. The 6-cluster solution reached a silhouette coefficient of .7, implying a good clustering quality. Significant differences between the clusters were detected in the proportions of all nursing diagnoses used as clustering variables. Table 2 reports these results in detail. The exact number of clusters was always achieved by repeating the cluster analysis four times on random subsamples of 50% of the cases. Moreover, these clusters had similar characteristics to those obtained by analysing the complete sample, which implies the stability of the solution.

5.4 | Comparison between clusters in demographic variables

Table 3 report descriptive results and comparisons between clusters for demographic variables, respectively. Significant differences were found between clusters in age. The clusters with the lowest age are two (Anxiety coping response) and four (Acute pain response.), with

TABLE 2 (a) Six-cluster solution and distribution of prevalence of nursing diagnosis by clusters. (b) Post-hoc comparison between clusters in nursing diagnoses.

Nursing diagnosis	Cluster 1 'Responses to security threats' (C1) n = 5618		Cluster 2 'Anxiety coping responses' (C2) n = 4719		Cluster 3 'Fear coping responses' (C3) n = 4206		Cluster 4 'Acute pain response' (C4) n = 5135		Cluster 5 'Responses to exacerbations of chronic diseases' (C5) n = 5421		Cluster 6 'Dyspnea response' (C6) N = 1689	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
00126. Deficient knowledge	29	5.51%	66	12.55%	24	4.56%	53	10.08%	343	65.21%	11	2.09%
00132. Acute pain	0	.00%	0	.00%	0	.00%	5135	99.53%	0	.00%	24	.47%
00146. Anxiety	442	7.30%	4719	77.95%	91	1.50%	671	11.08%	0	.00%	131	2.16%
00148. Fear	0	.00%	0	.00%	206	88.29%	479	10.05%	0	.00%	79	1.66%
00155. Risk for falls	5618	82.93%	0	.00%	528	7.79%	451	6.66%	0	.00%	177	2.61%
00032. Ineffective breathing pattern	0	.00%	0	.00%	0	.00%	0	.00%	0	.00%	1689	100.00%
00179. Risk for unstable blood glucose level	73	12.19%	22	3.67%	32	5.34%	9	1.50%	458	76.46%	5	.83%
00214. Impaired comfort	132	14.07%	56	5.97%	28	2.99%	62	6.61%	646	68.87%	14	1.49%
00035. Risk for injury	145	28.66%	18	3.56%	17	3.36%	32	6.32%	288	56.92%	6	1.19%
00004. Risk for infection	138	23.00%	22	3.67%	75	12.50%	96	16.00%	246	41.00%	23	3.83%
00051. Impaired verbal communication	87	19.82%	14	3.19%	33	7.52%	5	1.14%	283	64.46%	17	3.87%
00069. Ineffective coping	46	6.48%	91	12.82%	23	3.24%	15	2.11%	528	74.37%	7	.99%
00078. Ineffective health management	64	10.46%	65	10.62%	23	3.76%	15	2.45%	425	69.44%	20	3.27%
00085. Impaired physical mobility	188	27.33%	45	6.54%	27	3.92%	92	13.37%	308	44.77%	28	4.07%

Nursing diagnosis	Chi-square			Cluster 1 'Responses to security threats' (C1)	Cluster 2 'Anxiety coping responses' (C2)	Cluster 3 'Fear coping responses' (C3)	Cluster 4 'Acute pain response' (C4)	Cluster 5 'Responses to exacerbations of chronic diseases' (C5)	Cluster 6 'Dyspnea response' (C6)
	df	p							
00126. Deficient knowledge	685.84	5	<.001		C1 (<.001) C3 (=0.001)		C1 (=0.032)	C1 (<.001) C2 (<.001) C3 (<.001) C4 (<.001) C6 (<.001)	
00132. Acute pain	26635.85	5	<.001	a	a	a	a	a	
00146. Anxiety	19925.43	5	<.001	C3 (<.001)	a		C1 (<.001) C3 (<.001) C6 (<.001)	a	C3 (<.001)
00148. Fear	23302.53	5	<.001	a	a	a	C6 (<.001)	a	
00155. Risk for falls	21327.97	5	<.001	a	a	C4 (<.001)		a	

TABLE 2 (Continued)

Nursing diagnosis	Chi-square	df	p	Cluster 1 'Responses to security threats' (C1)	Cluster 2 'Anxiety coping responses' (C2)	Cluster 3 'Fear coping responses' (C3)	Cluster 4 'Acute pain response' (C4)	Cluster 5 'Responses to exacerbations of chronic diseases' (C5)	Cluster 6 'Dyspnea response' (C6)
00032. Ineffective breathing pattern	26788.00	5	<.001	a	a	a	a	a	a
00179. Risk for unstable blood glucose level	1217.97	5	<.001	C2 (<.001) C4 (<.001) C6 (=0.07)		C4 (<.001)		C1 (<.001) C2 (<.001) C3 (<.001) C4 (<.001) C6 (<.001)	
00214. Impaired comfort	1448.78	5	<.001	C2 (<.001) C3 (<.001) C4 (<.001) C6 (=0.01)				C1 (<.001) C2 (<.001) C3 (<.001) C4 (<.001) C6 (<.001)	
00035. Risk for injury	531.14	5	<.001	C2 (<.001) C3 (<.001) C4 (<.001) C6 (<.001)				C1 (<.001) C2 (<.001) C3 (<.001) C4 (<.001) C6 (<.001)	
00004. Risk for infection	212.92	5	<.001	C2 (<.001)		C2 (<.001)	C2 (<.001)	C1 (<.001) C2 (<.001) C3 (<.001) C4 (<.001) C6 (<.001)	C2 (=0.02)
00051. Impaired verbal communication	583.35	5	<.001	C2 (<.001) C3 (=0.10) C4 (<.001)		C2 (=0.022) C4 (<.001)		C1 (<.001) C2 (<.001) C3 (<.001) C4 (<.001) C6 (<.001)	C2 (=0.05) C4 (<.001)
00069. Ineffective coping	1354.11	5	<.001	C4 (=0.04)	C1 (<.001) C3 (<.001) C4 (<.001) C6 (<.001)			C1 (<.001) C2 (<.001) C3 (<.001) C4 (<.001) C6 (<.001)	
00078. Ineffective health management	957.20	5	<.001	C3 (=0.029) C4 (<.001)	C3 (=0.001) C4 (<.001)			C1 (<.001) C2 (<.001) C3 (<.001) C4 (<.001) C6 (<.001)	C4 (<.001)
00085. Impaired physical mobility	353.09	5	<.001	C2 (<.001) C3 (<.001) C4 (<.001) C6 (=0.05)			C2 (=0.006) C3 (<.001)	C1 (<.001) C2 (<.001) C3 (<.001) C4 (<.001) C6 (<.001)	C3 (=0.04)

Note: The darker the cell indicates, the higher its value. The lighter the cell indicates, the lesser its value.

Abbreviations: df, degrees of freedom.

^aNot used in comparison tests because the column ratio is zero or one.

means between 56 and 58 years old. Clusters three (Fear coping response) and five (Responses to exacerbations of chronic diseases) are the intermediate age clusters, with means between 61 and 63 years old. The clusters with the highest average age are cluster 1 (Responses to security threats), with an average age of 65 and cluster 6 (Dyspnea response), with an average of 5 years older than cluster 1, around 70 years old. Post hoc pairwise comparisons found differences between all clusters except for clusters 2 and 4 and clusters

3 and 5, that is, the two youngest clusters and the two intermediate age clusters described before.

Significant differences in gender were found between clusters. All the clusters are mostly made up of people identified as male, except for cluster 2 (Anxiety coping response), in which the female gender was the majority. In the pairwise comparisons, this cluster also determined the most significant differences in proportions with other clusters both in males and females.

FIGURE 1 Radar chart of prevalence of nursing diagnosis per clusters/cluster. The radial axis represents the prevalence of each diagnosis in each cluster, being the centre of the chart at 0% of prevalence and the edge at 100%. Nursing diagnoses are represented by their corresponding codes and clusters by their numbers. [Colour figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com)]

5.5 | Comparison between clusters in medical problems

Table 3 reports descriptives and comparisons between clusters for medical problems. Significant differences were found between clusters in the proportion of medical problems. Cases from all clusters were represented in all categories of medical problems considered. The most frequent medical problem was 'Other' in all clusters except in cluster 3, in which the most frequent category was 'Trauma', and in cluster 6, with the largest number of cases classified as 'Acute dyspnea'.

6 | DISCUSSION

The present study is the first to determine the prevalence of NANDA-I nursing diagnoses in an extensive data set of episodes of patients assisted by pre-hospital emergency teams recorded in EHR. Consequently, it has the largest sample among the few published studies on NANDA-I nursing diagnoses in the study setting. It is also the first to propose patterns in which nursing diagnoses are grouped. The results, therefore, will contribute to building evidence in this under-researched area.

The study population is made up primarily of middle-aged adults, with a higher percentage of men, with characteristics similar to those described previously in the studies developed in the Spanish pre-hospital care setting (Montero et al., 2016).

The first objective of this study was to determine the prevalence of NANDA-I diagnoses in the pre-hospital care setting. Five nursing

diagnoses accounted for 96.1% of all diagnoses recorded. The highest prevalence was for *Risk for falls* (00155) (safety/protection domain), followed by *Anxiety* (00146) (coping/stress tolerance domain), *Acute pain* (00132) (comfort domain), *Fear* (00148) (coping/stress tolerance domain) and *Ineffective breathing pattern* (00032) (Activity/rest domain). All of the diagnoses identified in our study have been described as prevalent in the pre-hospital setting in previous literature (Cámara & Valenzuela, 2007; Coca et al., 2020), which begins to generate consistent evidence about which human responses are most prevalent in the pre-hospital setting. It is noteworthy that *Risk for falls* (00155), which is the most prevalent diagnosis, was also the most prevalent diagnosis in the study by Coca et al. (2020), while in the study by Cámara and Valenzuela (2007), it was the second most prevalent diagnosis. These findings may be related to the high vulnerability suffered by patients attended by pre-hospital emergency teams and the appearance of autonomy problems described by Montero et al. (2016) and Coca et al. (2020). Similarly, this result shows the orientation towards patient safety in the care provided by the nurses of these teams (Bocanegra-Pérez et al., 2017; Montero et al., 2016). *Anxiety* (00146) is the only one of the diagnoses identified in our study that is among the top five most recorded in the three previous studies developed in this clinical context (Cámara & Valenzuela, 2007; Coca et al., 2020; Cyrillo et al., 2009). The coping/stress tolerance domain diagnoses *Anxiety* (00146) and *Fear* (00148) are not only in the top five diagnoses recorded in this study but also appear in 41.4% of all episodes studied. The literature describes the association between these human responses and the perception of feeling safe (Péculo-Carrasco et al., 2020, 2022) and with typical symptoms in patients assisted by emergency teams, such as dyspnea,

TABLE 3 (a) Cluster descriptives for sociodemographic variables and medical problems. (b) Post-hoc comparison between clusters in sociodemographic variables and medical problems.

		Cluster 1 'Responses to security threats' (C1) n = 5618		Cluster 2 'Anxiety coping responses' (C2) n = 4719		Cluster 3 'Fear coping responses' (C3) n = 4206		Cluster 4 'Acute pain response' (C4) n = 5135		Cluster 5 'Responses to exacerbations of chronic diseases' (C5) n = 5421		Cluster 6 'Dyspnea response' (C6) N = 1689		
		n/X	%/SD	n/X	%/SD	n/X	%/SD	n/X	%/SD	n/X	%/SD	n/X	%/SD	
(a)														
Age		65.37	18.70	56.96	19.48	61.50	19.26	57.88	19.05	62.12	19.60	70.81	15.29	
Gender	Male	3097	55.10%	1999	42.40%	2162	51.40%	2883	56.10%	3035	56.00%	888	52.60%	
	Female	2464	43.90%	2690	57.00%	2006	47.70%	2198	42.80%	2345	43.30%	795	47.10%	
	Unknown/ undetermined	57	1.00%	30	.60%	38	.90%	54	1.10%	41	.80%	6	.40%	
Medical problems	Trauma	595	11.90%	336	7.60%	623	16.30%	2011	39.90%	680	14.70%	31	1.90%	
	Stroke	351	7.00%	92	2.10%	135	3.50%	9	.20%	291	6.30%	13	.80%	
	Acute neurology (excluding stroke)	868	17.30%	236	5.30%	348	9.10%	74	1.50%	457	9.90%	17	1.00%	
	Chest pain	161	3.20%	380	8.60%	364	9.50%	683	13.60%	197	4.20%	17	1.00%	
	Acute cardiology	577	11.50%	381	8.60%	664	17.40%	917	18.20%	380	8.20%	61	3.70%	
	Acute dyspnea	172	3.40%	96	2.20%	107	2.80%	16	.30%	191	4.10%	784	47.30%	
	Others	2279	45.60%	2912	65.70%	1585	41.40%	1324	26.30%	2442	52.70%	734	44.30%	
	(b)													
		Statistic	df	p	Cluster 1 'Responses to security threats' (C1)	Cluster 2 'Anxiety coping responses' (C2)	Cluster 3 'Fear coping responses' (C3)	Cluster 4 'Acute pain response' (C4)	Cluster 5 'Responses to exacerbations of chronic diseases' (C5)	Cluster 6 'Dyspnea response' (C6)				
Age		1103.94 ^a	5	<.001	C2 (<.001) C3 (<.001) C4 (<.001) C5 (<.001)	C1 (<.001) C3 (<.001) C5 (<.001) C6 (<.001)	C1 (<.001) C2 (<.001) C4 (<.001) C6 (<.001)	C1 (<.001) C3 (<.001) C5 (<.001) C6 (<.001)	C1 (<.001) C2 (<.001) C4 (<.001) C6 (<.001)	C1 (<.001) C2 (<.001) C3 (<.001) C4 (<.001) C5 (<.001)	C1 (<.001) C2 (<.001) C3 (<.001) C4 (<.001) C5 (<.001)			
Gender	Male	287.23 ^b	10	<.001	C2 (<.001) C3 (= .004)	C1 (<.001) C3 (<.001) C4 (<.001) C5 (<.001) C6 (<.001)	C1 (= .004) C2 (<.001) C4 (<.001) C5 (<.001)	C2 (<.001) C3 (<.001)	C2 (<.001) C3 (<.001) C6 (= .033)	C3 (<.001)	C2 (<.001)			
	Female				C2 (<.001) C3 (= .002)	C1 (<.001) C3 (<.001) C4 (<.001) C5 (<.001) C6 (<.001)	C1 (= .002) C2 (<.001) C4 (<.001) C5 (<.001)	C2 (<.001) C3 (<.001) C6 (= .033)		C2 (<.001) C4 (= .033)				
	Unknown/ Undetermined													
Medical problems	Trauma	11029.42 ^b	30	<.001	C2 (<.001) C3 (<.001) C4 (<.001) C5 (= .001) C6 (<.001)	C1 (<.001) C3 (<.001) C4 (<.001) C5 (<.001) C6 (<.001)	C1 (<.001) C2 (<.001) C4 (<.001) C6 (<.001)	C1 (<.001) C2 (<.001) C3 (<.001) C5 (<.001) C6 (<.001)	C1 (= .001) C2 (<.001) C6 (<.001)	C1 (<.001) C2 (<.001) C3 (<.001) C4 (<.001) C5 (<.001)	C1 (<.001) C2 (<.001) C3 (<.001) C4 (<.001) C5 (<.001)			
	Stroke				C2 (<.001) C3 (<.001) C4 (<.001) C6 (<.001)	C4 (<.001) C6 (= .009)	C2 (= .001) C4 (<.001) C6 (<.001)		C2 (<.001) C3 (<.001) C4 (<.001) C6 (<.001)	C4 (= .003)				
	Acute neurology (excluding stroke)				C2 (<.001) C3 (<.001) C4 (<.001) C5 (<.001) C6 (<.001)	C4 (<.001) C6 (<.001)	C2 (<.001) C4 (<.001) C6 (<.001)		C2 (<.001) C4 (<.001) C6 (<.001)					

(Continues)

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TABLE 3 (Continued)

	Statistic	df	p	Cluster 1 'Responses to security threats' (C1)	Cluster 2 'Anxiety coping responses' (C2)	Cluster 3 'Fear coping responses' (C3)	Cluster 4 'Acute pain response' (C4)	Cluster 5 'Responses to exacerbations of chronic diseases' (C5)	Cluster 6 'Dyspnea response' (C6)
Chest pain				C6 (<.001)	C1 (<.001) C5 (<.001) C6 (<.001)	C1 (<.001) C5 (<.001) C6 (<.001)	C1 (<.001) C2 (<.001) C3 (<.001) C5 (<.001) C6 (<.001)	C6 (<.001)	
Acute cardiology				C2 (<.001) C5 (<.001) C6 (<.001)	C6 (<.001)	C1 (<.001) C2 (<.001) C5 (<.001) C6 (<.001)	C1 (<.001) C2 (<.001) C5 (<.001) C6 (<.001)	C6 (<.001)	
Acute dyspnea				C2 (= .003) C4 (<.001)	C4 (<.001)	C4 (<.001)		C2 (<.001) C3 (= .015) C4 (<.001)	C1 (<.001) C2 (<.001) C3 (<.001) C4 (<.001) C5 (<.001)
Others				C3 (= .002) C4 (<.001)	C1 (<.001) C3 (<.001) C4 (<.001) C5 (<.001) C6 (<.001)	C4 (<.001)		C1 (<.001) C3 (<.001) C4 (<.001) C6 (<.001)	C4 (<.001)

Note: The darker the cell indicates, the higher its value. The lighter the cell indicates, the lesser its value.

Abbreviation: df, degrees of freedom.

^aKruskal–Wallis.

^bChi-square.

acute or chronic pain (Kauppi et al., 2020; Lourens et al., 2019). Both diagnoses are equally present in patients cared for in different clinical settings (Mercês et al., 2021), such as intensive care units (Ferreira et al., 2016), obstetrics (Yang et al., 2019) and surgery (Noh & Lee, 2014), also, in multi-pathological patients (Villarejo, 2011) or with COVID-19 (Swanson et al., 2020). Based on our results, it can be affirmed that these are equally relevant human responses in pre-hospital emergencies. *Acute pain* (00132) and *Ineffective breathing pattern* (00032) are the other two diagnoses that complete the top five ranking with the highest prevalence. As mentioned above, acute pain and dyspnea are two of the main reasons for the need for emergency department attendance (Friesgaard et al., 2018; Kauppi et al., 2020; Lourens et al., 2019; Magnusson et al., 2021). Indeed, as in this study, Coca et al. (2020) and Cyrillo et al. (2009) identified these two problems as nursing diagnoses in patients assisted by pre-hospital emergency teams. The fact of identifying these symptoms as nursing diagnoses is crucial for developing stand-alone interventions that address the goals of improving patient comfort and sense of safety, among other benefits. Consequently, one of the main objectives of pre-hospital care for nurses should be the assessment, identification and intervention of pain and dyspnea in patients under care (Bocanegra-Pérez et al., 2017; Magnusson et al., 2021).

Identifying clusters of nursing diagnoses recorded in patients assisted by pre-hospital emergency teams was the second objective of this study. None of the studies developed in the pre-hospital emergency care setting mentioned above in this paper (Cámara & Valenzuela, 2007; Coca et al., 2020; Cyrillo et al., 2009; Montero

et al., 2016) reported information on how NANDA-I nursing diagnoses cluster. Six clusters of nursing diagnoses were found. In five of the identified clusters, a single diagnosis predominated in each cluster: *Risk for falls* (00155), *Anxiety* (00146), *Fear* (00148), *Acute pain* (00132) and *Ineffective breathing pattern* (00032). The sixth cluster agglutinates several human responses. All of them were related to chronic patient exacerbation, led by *Risk for unstable blood glucose level* (00179).

Cluster 1 (Responses to security threats) showed *Risk for falls* (00155) as the predominant diagnosis (safety/protection domain) together with several other diagnoses with residual prevalence focused mainly on the safety/protection and physical activity of the patients assisted. Different issues may have conditioned the formation of this cluster. Falls are a significant safety issue in health service quality programmes (Tanrikulu & Sari, 2017). For this reason, the care guidelines and protocols of the institution where this research was conducted emphasize the systematic assessment of the Risk of falls in assisted patients (Bocanegra-Pérez et al., 2017; Montero et al., 2016). The increased vulnerability to falls is primarily determined by the loss of autonomy for mobility and safety maintenance experienced by these patients (Montero et al., 2016). In addition, other factors in the pre-hospital setting increase the Risk of falls and affect patient safety, such as high average age, the administration of certain drugs with hemodynamic and neurological effects, an unfamiliar environment for the patient, and the ambulance transfer itself, among others (Herdman et al., 2021; Montero et al., 2016; Péculo-Carrasco et al., 2020, 2022; Pinto Okuno et al., 2015). It is, therefore,

not surprising that the first cluster was made up of diagnoses responding to security threats.

Clusters 2 (Anxiety coping response) and 3 (Fear coping response) were dominated by two diagnoses from the coping/stress tolerance domain, *Anxiety (00146)* and *Fear (00148)*, respectively. In cluster 2, together with *Anxiety (00146)* (77.95%), mainly diagnoses related to lack of knowledge and other forms of coping were grouped. In cluster 3, *Fear (00148)* (88.29%) appeared with diagnoses focused on patient safety risks and communication. Critical illness is perceived as a catastrophic event that may provoke coping responses in the patient (Sánchez-Almagro et al., 2022; Wesson, 1997). Different stressors, such as medical or nursing interventions, uncertainty, lack of previous experience and loss of autonomy (Montero et al., 2016), are present when a critically ill patient is admitted to the intensive care unit (Wesson, 1997). During hospitalization in these intensive care units, fear and distress were found to be feelings patients expressed about unexpected experiences and heightened vulnerability (Ruidiaz-Gómez & Fernández-Aragón, 2020). These stressors can also be observed in critically ill patients in the pre-hospital setting related to losing control of the situation. People call emergency services when they feel they cannot handle the situation alone (Kauppi et al., 2020). There is unanimity among studies conducted in the pre-hospital setting (Cámara & Valenzuela, 2007; Coca et al., 2020; Cyrillo et al., 2009), which determine that *Anxiety (00146)* and *Fear (00148)* are among the most recorded nursing diagnoses by nurses at the pre-hospital level. Whether anxiety and fear represent a feeling, an emotion, or a physiological and behavioural response, both phenomena come to be represented as human responses that could be intervened by the nurse (Mercês et al., 2021). Differentiating between the two diagnoses can be complex, and nurses may use them as if they have the same meaning (Mercês et al., 2021). Despite the differences in the definitions of each diagnosis, *Anxiety (00146)* and *Fear (00148)* are two human responses with shared clinical indicators that may be present in both diagnoses, acting as a confounding factor for decision-making in clinical practice (Mercês et al., 2021). Despite this, and based on the results obtained, these two diagnoses belonging to the coping/stress tolerance domain predominated in two of the six clusters obtained and should be considered relevant patterns in the care of pre-hospital patients.

Cluster 4 (Acute pain response) is dominated by the diagnosis of *Acute pain (00132)* (Comfort domain), together with diagnoses oriented towards safety/protection, physical activity, coping and lack of knowledge. Pain is one of the leading causes of the need for health care in hospitals and pre-hospital care (Friesgaard et al., 2018; Lourens et al., 2019; Magnusson et al., 2021). Therefore, forming a cluster with these responses is plausible in the context studied. Pre-hospital emergency teams are often the first to care for patients in emergencies with pain. The nurses in these teams can optimally treat these patients' acute pain (Magnusson et al., 2021). This optimization could include holistic pain management, regardless of aetiology. Mota et al. (2019) concluded that nurses focus on more than pharmacological measures to relieve pain and discomfort as, in their study, nurses developed non-pharmacological pain management

interventions. Situations such as chest pain, acute coronary syndrome or trauma have acute pain among their primary symptoms and may be associated with some coping responses (Andersson et al., 2017; Carnesten et al., 2021; Wibring et al., 2019). Anxiety is one of the most frequent emotions associated with pain (Cimpean & David, 2019).

Cluster 5 (Responses to exacerbations of chronic diseases) was the only cluster that did not show a single human response as predominant. It simultaneously groups nursing diagnoses applicable to exacerbations of chronic diseases with high prevalence. Chronic health problems constitute a challenge for health systems. The age of the patients assisted is increasing, presenting more complex needs in chronicity and co-morbidity (Mackintosh et al., 2020). These patients present to emergency departments when they experience a severe change in their baseline health status. Schumacher et al. (2017) describe the severity of symptoms, lack of adequate access to health services and the immediacy provided by emergency departments as some of the reasons for urgent medical care seeking by this type of patient (Schumacher et al., 2017). The exacerbation of chronic pathologies in a situation of co-morbidity and poly medication is nowadays one of the main reasons for assistance (EPES, 2021). Based on the identified diagnoses, these cases are grouped in cluster 5 (Responses to exacerbations of chronic diseases). Similarly, the diagnoses identified in our study make clinical sense with the symptoms recorded by nurses in chronic patients with problems such as COPD, diabetes, cancer or heart failure at the hospital level (Koleck et al., 2021) and the nursing diagnoses identified by Coca et al. (2020) in their study of chronic patients assisted by pre-hospital emergency teams.

The sixth cluster (Dyspnea response) showed the diagnosis of *Ineffective breathing pattern (00032)* (Activity/rest domain) as the predominant one. It is accompanied by human responses focusing mainly on physical activity, communication and safety/protection. Dyspnea or shortness of breath is among the most frequent reasons for seeking medical assistance from emergency medical services (EPES, 2021; Kauppi et al., 2020) and, as a symptom, it is a point of interest for nursing (Koleck et al., 2021). The impact of this symptom on patients was evidenced by the human responses that cluster with *Ineffective breathing pattern (00032): Impaired physical mobility (00085)* and *Impaired verbal communication (00051)*. In addition, coping responses such as anxiety and fear are commonly observed with dyspnea (Kauppi et al., 2020). Therefore, pre-hospital care nursing is essential in managing other concomitant responses in patients with dyspnea, including physical activity, communication and coping/stress tolerance issues. The formation of this cluster highlights the need for an integrated approach to care for patients with dyspnea in the pre-hospital setting.

Once the clusters have been established, discussing the differences between the patients in each cluster is necessary. Three age-differentiated clusters were found. The clusters with the youngest ages were clusters 2 and 4, 'Anxiety coping response' and 'Acute pain response', respectively. Studies in patients with anxiety or anxiety associated with pain considered a symptom, not a nursing diagnosis

(Dark et al., 2018; Musey et al., 2018; Patel et al., 2014). Lower ages were also found in another study on nursing interventions in patients with *Acute pain* (00132) in the hospital emergency department (Cavalheiro et al., 2019). These data support that these clusters present the youngest ages compared to the rest in the present study. Middle ages were shown in cluster 3, 'Fear coping response', and 5, 'Responses to exacerbations of chronic diseases'. Our results show younger ages than in the literature in chronic patients assisted by emergency teams (Coca et al., 2020). There are no specific studies on fear as a nursing diagnosis to compare our results. The higher ages shown in clusters 1, 'Responses to security threats', and 6, 'Dyspnea response' (the oldest of all clusters), are plausible with the association made by Herdman et al. (2021) between age 65 years or older and patient safety risks and the description of similar ages in patients presenting with dyspnea in the pre-hospital setting (Kauppi et al., 2020; Kelly et al., 2016).

Regarding gender, some differences were found between our results and findings in previous studies. Five clusters showed a higher prevalence of the male gender. Clusters 4 and 5, 'Acute pain response' and 'Responses to exacerbations of chronic diseases', show the highest prevalence of males compared to the rest of the clusters. However, Cavalheiro et al. (2019), in the study of nursing interventions in patients with a nursing diagnosis of *Acute pain* (00148) in hospital emergency departments, and Coca et al. (2020) when studying chronic patients assisted by pre-hospital teams reported a higher prevalence of women. As in the 'Responses to security threats' cluster 1, Montero et al. (2016) identified most men with needs that condition patient safety in the same context as our study. Clusters 6, 'Dyspnea response', and 3, 'Fear coping response', showed the lowest prevalence, respectively. There are no known results for *Fear* (00148) to compare the present study results. However, gender differences are again obtained concerning the results shown by Kauppi et al. (2020) and Kelly et al. (2016) in patients with dyspnea in the pre-hospital setting. The only cluster with the highest prevalence corresponding to the female gender was cluster 2, 'Anxiety coping response'. No specific studies have been found on *Anxiety* (00146) as a nursing diagnosis in the pre-hospital setting. However, at the hospital level, higher levels of perceived anxiety as a symptom have been documented in women compared to men among emergency department attendees for pain (Patel et al., 2014). It is also more prevalent in women who attend emergency departments for anxiety as a mental health problem (Dark et al., 2018). Both of these data may support our findings in this cluster.

Health care in the context of the study was directed towards medical problems related to altered levels of consciousness, trauma, dyspnea and non-traumatic pain. The category 'Others' encompasses various medical processes that cannot be classified into the other problems described and constitute the most significant volume of demand for care (EPES, 2020, 2021). Therefore, it is the most frequent category of medical problems patients present, classified into four clusters. In these clusters, 'Others' is joined by other medical categories with different prevalences, as described below. Cluster 1, 'Responses to security threats', has high prevalences in 'Acute

neurology', followed by 'Trauma' and 'Acute cardiology'. These clinical situations may affect the patient's autonomy for mobility and safety, prompting the nurse to ensure patient safety (Montero et al., 2016). Clusters 2, 'Anxiety coping response' and 3, 'Fear coping response', showed high prevalences of the medical problems 'Acute cardiology', 'Chest pain' and 'Trauma'. In addition to the possible impact on the life situation of these categories, acute pain is one of the main symptoms, whose association with coping responses is widely known (Andersson et al., 2017; Carnesten et al., 2021; Wibring et al., 2019).

Cluster 5, 'Responses to exacerbations of chronic diseases', showed the second highest prevalence of 'Others', followed by the categories 'Trauma', 'Acute Neurology' and 'Acute Cardiology'. All these clinical categories, except for 'Trauma', could present as flare-ups or exacerbations in patients with a previous chronic problem in these specialities. In contrast to the abovementioned clusters, the two with the highest prevalence of other clinical categories are described below. Cluster 4, 'Acute pain response', showed the highest prevalence of clinical categories where acute pain may be the main symptom, with 'Trauma' in the lead, followed by 'Others', 'Acute cardiology' and 'Chest pain'. Finally, cluster 6, 'Dyspnea response', showed the clinical category 'Acute dyspnea' with the highest prevalence, followed by 'Others' and with residual prevalence 'Acute cardiology', maintaining the clinical sense that has characterized each cluster. Based on these associations, nursing diagnoses do not cluster to specific medical problems, but all medical problems were represented in the patients classified in all clusters. Therefore, it is believed that one of the most relevant issues of the study is that a classification of the patient based on the human responses he/she presents is possible and that this classification is independent of the medical pathologies the patient presents. These findings may be the basis for a change in the classical approach of standardizing care according to the medical pathology of the patient in the pre-hospital setting. It may also change the usual design of the training of these nurses using guides and programmes based on extensive medical content and little content on the care that the nurse must provide autonomously. Nursing diagnosis clusters would benefit patients by meeting their care needs and impacting their safety and physical and psychological well-being. It would also make visible the nurse's autonomy and ability to solve these health problems independently. It also opens up several lines of research into the human responses present in these patients. NANDA-I defines a syndrome as a 'clinical judgment regarding a set of specific nursing diagnoses that occur together and are more correctly treated together through similar interventions' (Herdman et al., 2021). One of these lines of research may be oriented towards identifying diagnostic syndromes related to the health situation of these patients, such as that observed in the cluster "Responses to exacerbations of chronic diseases", where different nursing diagnoses converge, coinciding with previous studies (Coca et al., 2020). Furthermore, it provides new evidence that medical diagnoses do not condition nursing diagnoses, given that there would be no representation of patients with the different medical problems considered in all the

clusters if these were the case. Based on the results, it can be affirmed that the nursing diagnoses that patients in the pre-hospital setting derive more from the health situation they are experiencing and the signs and symptoms they present than from the type of medical problem.

7 | LIMITATIONS

This study has several limitations that need to be highlighted. First, a pre-hospital emergency care agency census from a single country allows us to determine the prevalence and clustering of nursing diagnoses in the patients attended by this agency. However, it makes it difficult to generalise the results to other settings. It would be appropriate to replicate this study in other national or international pre-hospital emergency agencies to corroborate the study results. Second, although conducting a census eliminates the possibility of random sampling error and selection bias (Daniel, 2012), an under-recording of nursing diagnoses of 50.62% of the total records was assumed. These missing data may have affected the prevalence and clustering results, even more so knowing that they are not missing at random, which means that the probability of being missing varies for unknown reasons. Future studies would be needed to address the missing data not at random by finding the causes of the omissions or by performing hypothetical analyses to determine the sensitivity of the results in different scenarios. Third, diagnostic accuracy was not evaluated, so there is an opportunity that a part of the nursing diagnoses had been recorded with low accuracy. Different elements influence the way nurses diagnose: the complexity of the patient's situation, the institution's diagnosis policy and the individual characteristics of the nurse herself, such as training, experience and attitude towards nursing diagnosis (Lumillo-Gutierrez et al., 2019; Paans et al., 2011; Park, 2014). These elements were not considered in this study. The high variability in the ability of nurses to execute care plans was also not controlled. However, the emergency care agency in which the study was carried out has fully implemented a practice nursing model which includes standardized nursing languages.

Moreover, professionals were explicitly trained, and an agency working group proposed standards of practice for implementing nursing diagnosis and application of the nursing process. In addition, audits of the records in the EHR system are continuously performed to determine whether they meet these standards. Both aspects favour the reduction of the previously assumed variability in diagnosis. However, it would be interesting to formally assess professionals' ability to make care plans and record them to establish improvement strategies. Finally, patients were categorized by their main medical problem, but it may be the case that they may suffer from more than one. Additional medical problems could also generate nursing diagnoses. This fact could have conditioned the finding that all medical problems were represented in patients of all groups.

8 | CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a cluster analysis was used to reveal profiles of the nursing diagnosis of patients who were attended to and transferred to the hospital by pre-hospital emergency care teams due to an emerging health problem. Six clusters of nursing diagnoses were identified in these patients. A predominant nursing diagnosis headed five clusters. According to previous literature, these predominant diagnoses within each cluster also coincide with human responses most frequently addressed in the pre-hospital setting. The sixth cluster is the exception in which several diagnoses with high prevalence co-occurred, all applicable to exacerbations of chronic diseases. Patients with various medical problems were classified in all nursing diagnosis clusters. These findings could discuss that human responses in pre-hospital patients are generated by the health situation they are experiencing and the signs and symptoms they present rather than by the medical problem they are suffering. Therefore, the identified nursing diagnosis clusters will allow managers to protocolize nursing care. Based on the human response patterns presented by the patient and not on their medical problems as it has been traditionally, implying a common nursing approach to patients with different medical problems.

Furthermore, this clinical-based knowledge will improve the quality of individualized and standardized care plans in the pre-hospital setting. The results of this study may also help educators contextualize this practice setting, helping to explain the patterns of human responses that occur in patients with emergent pathology, especially in terms of coping and the threat to safety that the situation produces and the impact of signs and symptoms. Similarly, identifying diagnoses that appear simultaneously in the pre-hospital context leads us to reflect on the possible existence of syndromic diagnoses. The certainty that nursing diagnoses occur together in people cared for by pre-hospital emergency care teams could lead to the formal identification of diagnostic syndromes, which can be proposed for inclusion in successive editions of the NANDA-I Diagnostic Classification.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

José Manuel Romero-Sánchez: Supervision, methodology, writing—review and editing, conceptualization, formal analysis, visualization; César Pedro Sánchez-Almagro: conceptualization, acquisition of data and interpretation of data, research, writing—original draft, review and editing; Melanie White-Ríos: Research, writing—original draft, review and editing; Olga Paloma-Castro: Supervision, conception, review and editing. All the authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

None of the authors has any conflict of interest to disclose.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that support the findings of this study are not available from the authors since they were used under licence from the Medical Emergency Center (CES 061) for the current study, and so are not publicly available.

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